

UDK: 334.7:330.3

**THE ROLE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES IN THE
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF AZERBAIJAN: A STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FOR
2023-2024**

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the importance, economic benefits, and role of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the country's economic system, as well as the outcomes of government support provided to this sector. Based on official statistical indicators, the study evaluates the share of SMEs in ensuring employment for the population and highlights their contribution to maintaining stability in the national labor market. The performance results of SME entities are assessed both collectively and individually in a comparative manner. It is concluded that the development of SMEs plays a decisive role in improving the socio-economic welfare of the country.*

Keywords: *small and medium-sized enterprises, concessional financing, employment, government support, value added.*

In the overall economic development of Azerbaijan, as well as in the structure of its economy, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) serve as one of the most important structural elements. These elements have significant socio-economic impacts in the country. SMEs are of strategic importance in terms of diversifying economic activity, reducing unemployment, promoting the development of economic regions, and overall improving the business environment and expanding opportunities. In particular, in recent years, the implementation of government-led stimulation and business promotion mechanisms-such as concessional financing, tax incentives, increased volumes of subsidies and grants, along with institutional reforms-has intensified the development of SMEs across all sectors in which they operate.

Based on the indicators released by the State Statistical Committee, it can be stated that SME representatives constitute the majority of economic entities operating in Azerbaijan. Micro-enterprises, in particular, hold a significant numerical advantage over other economic entities [1, p. 205]. This reflects the favorable business environment, the government's emphasis on competition by facilitating business entry, and the widespread nature of entrepreneurial activity in the country. Micro-entrepreneurship aims to increase employment through self-employment. The requirement to hire an additional three employees in order to benefit from tax incentives not only ensures financial flexibility but also stimulates business expansion. By taking advantage of these incentives and support measures, micro-enterprises can gradually increase their turnover and transition into small businesses. This factor fully reflects the transformation of business scale. It should be emphasized that SMEs contribute significantly to value creation by operating in relatively larger-scale and more capital-intensive sectors of the national economy.

To illustrate the representation of SMEs within the system of macroeconomic indicators, we present in Table 1 the relevant SME-related indicators selected from page 23 of the statistical publication titled "Micro, Small and Medium Entrepreneurship in Azerbaijan", published electronically by the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Table 1

Main macroeconomic indicators of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Republic of Azerbaijan						
Indicators	2023			2024		
	Total	Small business	Medium business	Total	Small business	Medium business
Value added (million manats)	12544,0	3254,9	9289,1	12380,0	3469,6	8910,4
Number of employees (thousand persons)	340,9	110,3	230,6	366,2	121,5	244,7
Average monthly wage (manats)	771,1	642,8	899,4	830,05	679,2	980,9
Investments in fixed capital (million manats)	2062,6	794,0	1268,6	2060,7	821,4	1239,3
Number of operating businesses	12016	8610	3406	13524	9737	3787

Source: [4. p. 23]

Table 1 includes indicators such as value added, the number of people employed in small and medium-sized enterprises, the average monthly wages paid to employees, investments made by SMEs in fixed capital, as well as the quantitative indicators of operating SMEs. As can be seen, the contribution of small businesses to the national economy in terms of value added increased in 2024 compared to 2023. This growth is associated with the significant increase in the number of micro-enterprises, the rising dynamics of their transformation into small businesses, the expansion of production volumes, and the development observed in the service sector of the country. The monetary volume of value added created by medium-sized enterprises in the national economy is approximately 2,5 times higher than that of small businesses. However, a slight decline in dynamics has been observed in this segment. Overall, medium-sized enterprises demonstrate relatively higher productivity compared to small businesses [4, p. 23].

The employment indicators presented in Table 1 also reflect the importance of SMEs in providing employment across various sectors of economic activity. These economic entities play a significant role in ensuring employment for a large portion of the population and contribute to maintaining stability in the national labor market. The number of employees working in medium-sized enterprises is higher than in small businesses, and these entities provide more job opportunities for citizens. Naturally, the development of SMEs plays a decisive role in improving the socio-economic welfare of the country.

The indicators presented in Table 1 reflect both the overall growth in employment within SMEs and structural changes across segments. According to the data, while the total number of employed persons was 340.9 thousand in 2023, it increased to 366,2 thousand in 2024. This indicates an increase of approximately 25,3 thousand employed individuals in the labor market and confirms the overall expansion of business activity.

Employment in small businesses increased from 110,3 thousand in 2023 to 121,5 thousand in 2024, representing an increase of 11,2 thousand people. This growth indicates the strengthening role of small business entities in providing employment to citizens. In medium-sized enterprises, the

number of employees rose from 230,6 thousand in 2023 to 244,7 thousand in 2024, which corresponds to an annual increase of 14,1 thousand people. This indicator shows that medium-sized enterprises are also one of the main driving forces of employment in the country.

From a structural perspective, in both analyzed years, the share of medium-sized enterprises was higher than that of small businesses. In 2023, medium-sized enterprises accounted for approximately 67,7% of total employment, while small businesses made up 32,3%. In 2024, this proportion remained almost unchanged, and the dominance of medium-sized enterprises continued. This indicates that medium-sized enterprises-though not large-scale, but more stable and possessing broader production capacity-carry the main burden of the labor market and become the primary source of income for the population [5, p. 166]. Overall, the observed growth in both business segments reflects an increase in macroeconomic activity and a relative strengthening of the business environment [3, p.172]. While small businesses in Azerbaijan demonstrate more flexible and dynamic growth, medium-sized enterprises act as the main stabilizing factor of employment [2, p. 38].

In general, the analysis suggests that both the number of SMEs and their economic contribution are increasing in the country's economy. In particular, small business entities show more dynamic development. However, the lack of significant growth in investments in fixed capital indicates that this expansion is mainly driven by the establishment of new business entities rather than large-scale capital investments. Substantial investment volumes remain relatively stable. In contrast, medium-sized enterprises demonstrate stability across all directions, including investments and the growth in the number of newly established businesses.

In conclusion, it should be noted that SMEs in Azerbaijan act as one of the leading drivers of economic growth. The development of these entities contributes to the intensification of activities in non-oil sectors-considered a priority area for the country-as well as to the enhancement of export potential and the establishment of a sustainable and resilient economy. In the future, in order to further improve the quality of SME activities, it is essential to stimulate innovation-oriented economic activity, facilitate easier access to more favorable financial resources, and continue and expand institutional support mechanisms across various sectors.

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